

ECONOMICS

WAYS TO FORM LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF SME MANAGERS IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract

Nowadays, it has become clear that people are the most important factor in any enterprise in society, and they have tried to benefit from this element at the highest level. One of the important characteristics of a person is leadership. Especially in the recruitment of new employees in organizations and in the work they will do as managers, leadership characteristics are coming to the fore. It can be said that people with high leadership power increase the organization's efficiency a significant extent and thus participate in the organization in a positive direction. For this reason, leadership has gained even more relevance today. In the article, the modern management system and the leadership models corresponding to it, the types of leader behavior and the effects of the leader on the management system, and the ways of forming leadership characteristics in them are examined.

Keywords: small business, leadership, manager, management, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Small business entities are the basis of large enterprises, which are vital to the country's economy and are considered a dynamic structure for economies. If we consider the origin of large enterprises that are considered successful, it is seen that most of them are old, small enterprises with healthy development prospects. In small business entities, which constitute a significant part of the enterprises in the economic system, the number of business owners and employees who continue their lives with the income they receive from these enterprises is quite high. For this reason, small business entities are important from economic and social perspectives. [2]

As we know, leadership is a broad and valuable concept. Leadership is a rare management quality. A leader is a person who influences, guides, and coordinates people in the organization to achieve organization goals or a leader is not just any person but has characteristics that make him a leader. However, a leader is a person who leads his followers not only with his characteristics but also with his behaviors. Leadership is a process of influencing individual and group behavior to achieve common goals. [3]

One of the main strategic goals of the "Strategic Roadmap for the Production of Consumer Goods at the Level of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in the Republic of Azerbaijan", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated December 6, 2016, is to increase the knowledge and skills of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs. To ensure the implementation of the issues arising from the Strategic Roadmap, a seminar on the topic "Application of International Accounting Standards by SMEs" was held on October 14, 2019, at the Financial Sciences Education Center of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The main goal of the seminar was to

promote the application of International Accounting Standards by SMEs. [1]

Since leadership is a process of influencing others, it is not possible to talk about leadership alone. Leadership requires relationships with other people. Therefore, when trying to understand the process of leadership, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the people with whom the leader interacts. The behaviors and roles exhibited by leaders are formed by the value judgments of the people with whom they interact. Four important factors that affect leadership in SMEs. These are:

- First, the individual abilities and personality traits of the leader.
- Second, the characteristics and expectations of the organization or group.
- Third, the situation in which the relationship between the leader and the audience emerges.
- The existence of common goals between the leader and the followers.
- Leadership is a function of these four main factors.

Leadership is a concept with social, psychological and political dimensions. Leadership, in general terms, describes the power of influence that one person has over another or, more commonly, the influence of one or more people on large masses. Since leadership is the process of directing group actions and influencing others to achieve group goals, leadership can also be explained as the ability to convince others to realize certain goals with enthusiasm and excitement. In other words, leadership is the process of people using economic, political, or similar power and values to mobilize their audience to achieve goals that they have created independently or mutually. Leadership is the ability to collect information to gather a group of people around certain goals and to mobilize them to realize

these goals. Another meaning is the ability to influence group members in order to fulfill the goals of a group. Therefore, leadership is also used in the sense of the ability to realize the influence of group members by providing and developing problem-solving and goal-reaching skills for any group. "Leadership" is the process of influencing, directing and controlling the activities of a person or group in any case in order to achieve the goal; at the same time, it is the process of bringing the members of the group together and ensuring the continuation of the group.

If a leader is self-aware, always monitoring their own actions, then they can consciously influence those around them through their emotions and actions. It is important to initially be in a self-aware leadership position but also to have a team that is obedient to you, with a clear understanding of your strengths and weaknesses. [5]

Leadership is a process of social interaction. It is not just a process specific to formal organizations. We can talk about leadership in every field where there are human relationships. It is not necessary for the leader to be equipped with official powers. A leader who does not have official powers can also drag the masses behind him. However, being full of official persons can increase the sources of power that the leader can use. Leadership is not only at the top levels of the organization. Leadership is a process of using power. But it is not a process that begins only with strength but also requires advice, trust, love, and patience.

Modern views on leadership in business activities are that it is necessary to change management characteristics according to the specific employee under his/her control. The fact that the most important element in business activities and organizations is a person and the necessity of organizing the human element to meet their needs and achieve goals, makes leadership and management necessary. For this reason, the existence of organizations also brings leadership in itself. However, discussions about what leadership is specifically have not yet yielded full results. The topic of leadership itself raises more questions than answers. Research on this topic is still very relevant and interesting today. However, when briefly explaining the concept of leadership, its characteristics can be summarized in 3 main groups:

- Intellectual characteristics: This includes characteristics such as thinking, general culture, logical analysis-synthesis ability, emotional power, ability to imagine, and ability to judge.

- Characteristic characteristics: Characteristics such as adaptation, attention, caution, initiative, memory power, stability, regularity, dynamism, seriousness.

- Social characteristics: Appearance, ability to address and understand the group, work discipline, cooperation, self-regulation, etc. are characteristics.

Leaders have three basic tasks in SME managers. These are to mobilize employees, remove obstacles and weakened performance, and motivate their followers. People did not notice the importance of leaders as much when they lived in peace, tranquility, security and comfort. On the contrary, in times of great changes, when

the crisis and chaos prevailed and distrust became popular, they began to search for leaders who would show them the way to get out of this situation. This is also true for business organizations. Leaders are the most important elements in the organizational structure because they are at the head of the masses, at the top of organizations, and have great influence on societies. Japan has shown the best example of this. Because the socio-economic success that Japan has shown in front of America, which holds the world global market, was explained by the importance they gave to organizational culture. Since people are an important element in the dynamics of change, conducting field research in organizations where they spend a large part of their lives and where organizational culture awareness is embedded may be considered a suitable option.

The stronger your team is, the stronger you will be. For this reason, you should support your employees and prepare them for any difficult task. This not only strengthens the team, but also allows them to deal with more complex tasks. Thus, your team will be more motivated, disciplined and determined to your goals.

Leadership qualities: Along with the finances and equipment of any organization, its human resources are also among the main assets of this organization. In this sense, it is extremely important to think carefully when making decisions related to human resources, just like when making any financial or production decisions in the company. Inevitable, leaders are also involved in making these decisions. Or do leaders have any influential role in making such decisions?

Leadership concept: Everyone would agree that leadership is a broad concept. If we list the qualities required of a team leader, it will probably be more than the list of his job responsibilities. Studies have shown that two out of every ten leaders in companies do not have the necessary skills to take this company forward in the future. So how can leadership qualities be determined? You can determine importance of leadership qualities using various data or this, I recommend that you use ADAPT.

The ADAPT criteria include the skills of anticipating, driving, accelerating, partnering, and trusting. Let's take a look at these skills one by one: anticipating combines the following: a) the ability to understand the context and essence to make quick judgments and shape opportunities; b) the ability to focus on the social needs the organization seeks to serve; c) the ability to lead and coordinate collective efforts even in the face of uncertainty.

- Driving combines the following: a) the ability to inspire people by instilling a sense of achievement; b) creating an environment conducive to people being filled with hope, optimism, and intrinsic motivation; and c) the ability to manage mental and physical energy in oneself and others.

- Accelerating combines the following: a) managing the flow of knowledge to create sustainable innovations and achieve desired results; b) implementation of approaches for the operational creation of prototypes and iterations for the transformation of ideas into business and their agile implementation and dynamic processes.

- Partnership skills combine the following: a) building relationships and partnerships despite the foggy future of the economy; b) stimulating exchange; c) combining complementary competencies to ensure high efficiency.

- Trust, the ability to trust combines the following: a) the formation of new relationships between the organization and the individual aimed at mutual growth; b) the integration of different ideas and values; and c) helping employees discover the meaning of their activities and create maximum value.

Approaches related to leadership are grouped into four main groups:

- Trait approach
- Behavioral approaches
- Situational approaches
- Modern approaches.

The first significant theoretical approach to leadership is the trait approach. This theoretical concept establishes a very close relationship between leadership and the individual characteristics of the person who is the leader. Initially, it was claimed that individuals who become leaders were born with these characteristics, over the time it was accepted that leadership characteristics could also be acquired or developed through education. To determine the characteristics of a good leader, many studies have been carried out in line with the trait approach, as a result, the characteristics a leader should possess have been revealed. Among them, it has been stated that there are factors such as control ability, intelligence, decision-making ability, and self-confidence. [4]

Behavioral approaches, the trait approach to leadership analysis, have been developed as a result of researchers concentrating on the individual characteristics of leaders, focusing on how they behave and what they do. The basic content of this rule is that the behavior of the leader is formed more than the personal characteristics of the leader. Therefore, the relationship between the leader and his audience does not depend on the leaders characteristics but on whether his behavior and behavior are accepted by the group. Therefore, the leader cannot be thought separately and independently from the group he leads, and must be evaluated in terms of his relationship with the group. This rule, which focuses on behavior, leads to the discrimination of effective and ineffective leaders. This rule, in contrast to the trait rule, focuses on behaviors, behaviors can be learned and individuals can be trained; therefore, they can be provided with better leadership. Among the empirical and applied studies on behavior, Ohio State University, which has grouped the behavior of leaders into two separate dimensions: Consideration of human relations and Initiating Structure, continues to investigate these studies. The four variables that influence how a leader should behave can be defined as:

- Individual characteristics of the leader
- Individual characteristics of the followers
- Group characteristics
- Structural characteristics of the organization.

From here, changes in any or all of the factors will naturally affect the leader's attitude and behavior.

There are also many theories within the situational approaches. Although Fiedler began his work with the behavioral approach, he later put forward a different idea due to his research. The ideas of the scientist who developed the approach called "leader effectiveness", which is especially evaluated within the situational approach, and who divided leader behaviors into two, task-oriented and relationship-oriented, are very important in this field. According to Fiedler, a leader's behavior is fixed and cannot be easily changed. Therefore, it is more effective to bring the conditions in the organization into line with the leader's style rather than trying to change the leader's behavior.

Modern approaches With the development that emerged in the 1980s, leadership research has resulted in many different theoretical perspectives. Along with these perspectives, which are called modern approaches, many theoretical perspectives such as charismatic leadership, conversion leadership, interactionist leadership, visionary leadership, etc. have entered the leadership literature. On the basis of these perspectives, there are concepts such as transformation, vision, empowerment, development and social responsibility. With these perspectives, a two-way interaction and communication path opens between the leader and the followers. It would be appropriate to explain some of these leadership approaches. Charismatic leadership is a concept that is gaining popularity. Charisma is the ability to attract people and is open to development through education. The religious motif in the early examples of this type of leadership is consistent with Weber's thesis that charisma can also be applied to non-religious figures. Charismatic leaders are distinguished by their high level of power, self-confidence, and conviction and have a significant impact on the emotions of their audience. Max Weber and Charismatic Leadership Charisma dates back to the ancient Greek civilization and means "divine inspiration." Leaders should not lead by telling people what to do. Instead, leaders should make people want to help them. A key part of this is to develop your desire to help others. When others see that you want to help them, they will help you. Understanding social networks and the key influencers within them is another key part of leadership. Who has the most power in the organization, both formally and informally? Who is the heart of the group? Of course, these are all characteristics of a CSO leader.

In addition to all this, it should be noted that the establishment of a support organization is at the forefront of the support mechanisms for SMEs by the state. In the short term, the main direction of the organization's activities is to support the development of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship, increase the role of SMEs in the country's economy, protect their interests, provide services to entrepreneurs on a single platform, and coordinate state and private activities. In short, the organization assists at all stages of its activities, from the creation of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship entities to existing state support mechanisms and services, and plays a bridge role between state institutions and SMEs. The SME Friend currently established within the state is one of such mechanisms.

The creation of the SME Friend concept is directly related to the goals and objectives of the agency.

Thus, being a friend of the entrepreneur is at the forefront of the agency's main goals. The Small and Medium Business Agency supports micro, small, and medium-sized entrepreneurs in the places where SME friends operate, at all stages of the creation and development of new SME entities, as well as in protecting the rights of entrepreneurs, to identify and implement their initiatives and potential opportunities.

In addition, it is recommended that SMEs use financial instruments such as futures, forwards, options, swaps, and factoring as alternative and cheap sources of financing, increase interest in alternative sources of financing such as swaps and factoring, and expand financing opportunities for SMEs.

Ensuring sustainable economic development in the Azerbaijani state, and increasing the role of small and medium-sized enterprises in the economy is one of

the main priorities of our President I. Aliyev in the socio-economic development strategy.

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